

Machine Learning Model Adaptations for Execution in Energy-Constrained Intermittent Systems

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Abstract—With the global deployment of more Internet of Things (IoT) devices, the demand for running increasingly complex applications, such as predicting parameters in intricate systems or processing audio and images within the machine learning domain, has driven adaptations to existing models to lower memory and computational demands. Meanwhile, intermittent computing has brought forth a new paradigm for embedded, energy-constrained systems, requiring further modifications to the machine learning models and algorithms. Using approximate computing concepts to enable model execution in a transient energy environment has shown promising results. While advances in intermittent machine learning have enabled more neural network applications to be developed, many techniques and models haven't been widely tested and optimized yet. This work proposes conducting a comprehensive survey and outlines initial findings, positing further research needs to be done to understand the current scenario of intermittent machine learning and discover possible advances.

Index Terms—intermittent computing, machine learning, model compression, microcontrollers, Internet of Things

I. INTRODUCTION

A surge in Internet of Things (IoT) devices worldwide has been accompanied by the development of software frameworks and hardware accelerators to perform more complex operations and execute more demanding algorithms on less resourceful computing systems, such as machine learning models [1]. The advent of LiteRT [2] (formerly TensorFlow Lite), which is a runtime for artificial intelligence algorithm deployment in embedded systems, has enabled novel applications in the low-power embedded domain for micro-controllers previously unaccounted-for: those demanding machine learning usage. This was due to the challenges in developing meaningful applications, considering the huge resource scarcity. Moreover, hardware accelerators have been developed, as well as microcontrollers specifically for executing machine learning and, more generally, artificial intelligence applications, such as the LEA Accelerator in the MSP430FR board series¹, the

MAX78000 by Maxim Integrated², and the ESP32-S series by Espressif Systems³.

Machine learning models, ranging from linear regression through support vector classifiers to very complicated deep neural networks, can provide great insight into datasets, such as those collected by sensor nodes deployed in a wireless sensor network (WSN) [3]. This can be true for both predicting future results in a time series or parameters in a complex system being monitored [4] or for clustering the results obtained into more manageable subsets, reducing excess communication and improving energy efficiency [5]. Image and audio processing in the embedded devices is also a novel and promising trend, considering the increased accuracy obtained by employing machine learning models in those domains, compared to the classic algorithms [6] [7]. Allowing execution of those complex statistical analysis tools locally on the edge devices, ranging from very low-power microcontrollers to single-board computers, such as a Raspberry Pi, can reduce network traffic and also the wait time for a result to be provided to the end user while increasing data throughput [8]. Moreover, communication is quite expensive and can consume large amounts of power, which could be used in more immediately relevant computations [9].

In tandem with developing machine learning frameworks and accelerators for microcontrollers, energy harvesting technologies have been thoroughly explored over the past decade. By drawing power from environmental sources, battery-free operation becomes viable, reducing the environmental impact associated with the rapid increase in IoT devices. This allows for untethered use and enables novel applications previously limited by the constant maintenance requirements of batteries. However, executing meaningful programs in this domain significantly differs from conventional execution models, leading to a new computing paradigm: intermittent computing. By creating new frameworks and adapting existing ones to accommodate the variable energy supply from harvested sources,

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¹Texas Instruments, Low-Energy Accelerator (LEA) Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ), Document SLAA720, Nov. 2016.

²Maxim Integrated, Artificial Intelligence Microcontroller with Ultra-Low-Power Convolutional Neural Network Accelerator, MAX78000 Datasheet, May 2021.

³Espressif Systems, ESP32-S3-WROOM-1 & WROOM-1U Datasheet v1.3, ESP32-S3 Datasheet, 2023.

intermittent operation has become less challenging and increasingly beneficial. Nonetheless, further research is essential to optimize performance in this intermittent environment [10].

By combining machine learning models and algorithms with intermittent computing, new advancements can be achieved to enhance the sustainability of the Internet of Things. As an example, reinforcement learning has been explored as a way to optimize energy usage [11]. However, machine learning models are typically sensitive to contexts where data is faulty, inconsistent, or otherwise discrepant in formats and values. Such scenarios often arise due to intermittency — where computing intermittency may lead to incomplete results, and communication intermittency can cause invalid data packets — necessitating additional mechanisms to mitigate these issues and ensure reliable execution [9].

Another promising approach involves improving quality-of-service metrics, such as minimizing response times and increasing the frequency of value updates. This can be achieved by enabling local model execution on energy-constrained and computationally limited devices, therefore reducing communication latency. However, achieving this requires significant modifications to neural network models, reducing memory and computational demands [12] and enabling energy- and intermittence-aware execution [9]. Various techniques, such as quantization [13], [14], pruning [15] [16], tensor decomposition [17] [18], knowledge distillation [19] and neural architecture search [20], have been developed to support these changes. Some techniques, notably quantization, and pruning, have already been incorporated into frameworks like LiteRT, which enable machine learning model execution on microcontroller devices, achieving substantial model size reduction while maintaining high accuracy [21]. Additionally, approximate computing methods — primarily related to anytime algorithms, which facilitate a trade-off between energy consumption and accuracy [22] - provide greater flexibility. By employing early or multi-exit algorithms and models [22] [23], it becomes possible to trade the reduced accuracy for an increase in data throughput, which can be acceptable or even advantageous depending on a system's operational requirements [24].

II. RELATED WORKS

Several studies have developed deep neural network (DNN) models with adaptations to enable execution in intermittent environments. For instance, [22] introduces a multi-exit architecture and leverages quantization and pruning among the previously mentioned compression techniques. These rates are optimized by a multi-agent reinforcement learning algorithm, with rewards based on the average accuracy across all exits given an available energy trace. An online algorithm determines exit selection by assessing whether to proceed with additional inference or to exit early, balancing energy availability against the reduced accuracy resulting from not executing the entire network. As each exit requires specific training, the training process prioritizes the accuracy of the most likely exits. Another work, *ePerceptive* [23], proposes

modifications to enhance the perceptive abilities of low-power devices using DNNs. Its neural network architecture accommodates various input resolutions, recognizing that lower-resolution data usually requires lower energy consumption. Furthermore, similarly to the previous approach, multiple exits enable the network to produce valid outputs even under conditions of energy scarcity. Model compression techniques like quantization and pruning have been effectively applied in intermittent scenarios. Some studies [22] have combined these techniques with architectural modifications, while others have concentrated on optimizing pruning specifically for intermittent environments [16].

III. FUTURE WORKS

Despite significant architectural modifications proposed and executed in recent years, incorporating compression techniques into model design and further adjustments are still required for optimal execution. Multi- or early exiting, which has already been implemented, is just one of the approximate computing paradigm approaches that can be implemented for machine learning models. Meanwhile, among model compression techniques, the application of knowledge distillation and tensor decomposition in an intermittent environment has been lacking. Classically, quantization and pruning have been more explored, though there has been an interest in intermittent neural architecture search recently [20]. Moreover, most works have restricted themselves to neural network models and mostly convolutional [22], [23]. Support vector machines have been adapted to implement an anytime algorithm approach [24], but other machine learning architectures have been largely unexplored. Given the emerging nature of the field, conducting a survey could provide valuable insights into its current state and highlight potential areas for future advancements.

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